

**A Study on the Impact of Level of Happiness to the Academic Performance of Golden Faith Academy
Senior High School Students**

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I. Introduction

This chapter presents an introduction to this study. It covers the background of the study, statement of the problem, and significance of the study. The scope and delimitation and operational definition of terms are also explained at the end of this chapter.

A. Background of the Study

Happiness

An emotional state characterized by feelings of joy and pleasure is called happiness (Cherry, 2022). It is subjective and varies among individuals based on their personal beliefs and life experiences (Craig, 2019). Higher happiness levels have been linked to better physical health and lower levels of depression (American Heart Association, 2020; Kim et al., 2018). Despite these benefits, the annual Global Emotions Report has revealed that global happiness is declining, with the 2021 Negative Experience Index scoring 33, the highest ever recorded (Gallup, 2022).

Happiness among Teenage Students

The Youth Risk Behavior Survey also indicated that 42% of students felt persistent sadness (Garza, 2023). These feelings are commonly associated with social and emotional changes during adolescence (Terver, 2016). Schools have implemented plans to improve students' overall mood, including extracurricular activities (Buckley & Lee, 2021). Extracurricular activities are activities that students can participate in outside of their regular classes, such as clubs, volunteer work, and competitions (Llego, 2022). These activities have been associated with lower mental health problems and higher happiness levels (Gadermann et al., 2020).

Impact of Happiness on Academic Performance

A Harvard Graduate School of Education article stated that happiness can affect a student's motivation and academic performance (Bauld, 2021). Academic performance is defined as a student's ability to meet the academic standards set by a school or institution (Briones et al., 2021). The General Weighted Average (GWA) is a standard method of calculating students' academic performance by averaging grades per subject in a given academic period (University of the Philippines, 2019). Students who report higher happiness tend to achieve better academic performance (Gunasekara & Jayasekara, 2021). However, others concluded that there is no association between students' happiness and their academic performance (Chen et al., 2019). As a

result, further research is needed to comprehensively understand the impact of level of happiness on academic performance.

B. Statement of the problem

This study aims to study the impact of level of happiness to the academic performance of Golden Faith Academy Senior High School students. Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the positive impacts of level of happiness on academic performance on Golden Faith Academy Senior High School students?
2. What are the negative impacts of level of happiness on academic performance on Golden Faith Academy Senior High School students?

C. Significance of the Study

This study hopes to give awareness about the positive and negative impacts of level of happiness on academic performance among Golden Faith Academy Senior High School students. This study may also provide benefits to the following groups:

For the students, the study may provide insights into how happiness can affect their academic performance.

For the parents, the study may serve as a resource for understanding the role of happiness in their child's academic performance.

For the school, the study may inform the development of policies and programs that promote happiness among students.

For future researchers, the study can be used as a reference for those who are interested in exploring the impacts of happiness on academic performance.

D. Scope and Delimitation

This study will focus solely on the data from this school without attempting to generalize the results to other populations. It will also only evaluate the students' academic performance for this specific school year. Previous academic performances of the students will not be included.

E. Operational Definition of Terms

This section provides a clear and concise definition of the key terms used. It can also help reduce any misinterpretation from this study. The key terms used are defined as follows:

1. Students - These are individuals who are currently enrolled at Golden Faith Senior High School Academy.
2. Parents - These are individuals who have a child or children who are currently enrolled at Golden Faith Senior High School Academy.
3. School - This refers to the specific school of this study, which is Golden Faith Academy Senior High School.
4. School year - This refers to the academic year 2022-2023 at Golden Faith Academy Senior High School.

II. Review of Related Literature

This chapter gives an overview of relevant literature for this study. It is divided into two parts: foreign and local studies and research gap. Both of which are crucial to the current state of knowledge on this research topic.

A. Foreign and Local Studies

Students who are happier tend to be more engaged and motivated in their studies, leading to better academic performance (Ann et al., 2020). Higher levels of happiness can increase a students' academic performance, and vice versa (Jamil et al., 2020). This is consistent with a study that found that these two variables are correlated (Ali, 2022). This is why it has been suggested that promoting happiness may be an effective strategy for enhancing students' academic performance (Bugra & Furkan, 2021).

However, Langevin (2013) noted that higher levels of happiness may not necessarily translate to better academic performance. Many studies failed to find a statistically significant relationship between these two variables (Naderi et al., 2021; Otaghi et al., 2020). Amelia (2020) explained that there is no relationship between these two variables because students strive for academic success regardless of their level of happiness. This lack of consistent findings is attributed to various external factors that can impact happiness and academic performance (Ahirwar & Kewalramani, 2018).

Demographic profile of students can have a significant impact on happiness and academic performance. Male students showed a correlation between higher levels of happiness and academic performance, while no correlation among female students (Chui & Wong, 2015). A positive correlation between these two variables was observed for students who do not come from a broken family but not among those who do (Boye-Laryea, 2020). In terms of academic strands, ABM students tend to perform better academically, while those in HUMSS and GAS are generally less happy (Santos, 2019; Ablen et al., 2021). Higher grade levels can also lead to reduced levels of happiness, which can negatively impact their academic performance (Mertoglu, 2020).

Furthermore, the Oxford Happiness Questionnaire (OHQ) short form would be employed in this study. This research instrument was originally a 29-item questionnaire. Eventually, the OHQ short form was developed, which comprises eight questions from the original questionnaire. The OHQ short form is widely used to identify a student's level of happiness. The validity and reliability of this questionnaire were proven among students (Balootbangan et al., 2016). The General Weighted Average (GWA) would also be used to

assess academic performance. This procedure is similar to a study that found no relationship between the level of happiness and academic performance that was achieved using the OHQ and GWA (Belga, 2016).

B. Research Gap

The current understanding of how happiness impacts academic performance is limited. The majority of these studies were conducted in a foreign setting and at a different timeframe. To fill this gap, this study will investigate how the level of happiness impacts academic performance in a local setting. It will be conducted during the year 2023 to make a timely and relevant contribution to this topic.

III. Research Framework

This chapter presents the research framework of this study. This will help explain the variables of this study. This will also describe different aspects that influence this study.

The research framework's paradigm that will help this study is symbolic interactionism. Symbolic interactionism highlights the importance of social interactions in shaping individuals' identities and behaviors (Carter & Fuller, 2015). This paradigm mainly focuses on the psychological concepts of an individual and emphasizes the importance of subjective experiences (Franzese & Seiger, 2020). This is also relevant since this study aims to identify the impact of level of happiness on academic performance by considering different experiences of students.

The conceptual framework is utilized in this study because it gives an overview of the interrelationships between the study's variables (Adom et al., 2018). Conceptual framework can ensure that the data is more grounded and provides a structured and systematic approach (Gardner et al., 2022). This framework is commonly developed using the theories that are related in a study (Ponte et al., 2017).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The first theory used in this study is the Broaden-and-Build Theory, created by psychologist Barbara Fredrickson in 1998 (Fredrickson, 2013). It suggests that positive emotions, like happiness, can help people develop new skills and build social connections (Bigdeli & Rahimi, 2014). This theory also suggests that higher happiness levels can help students be more creative and do better in school by giving them the tools they need to learn, and helping them build good relationships with others (Alves et al., 2021).

The second theory that this study used is Self-Determination Theory (SDT). It was developed by psychologists Edward Deci and Richard Ryan in 1985 (Hoang et al., 2023). The SDT states that individuals have four basic psychological needs: autonomy, competence, relatedness, and beneficence (Martela & Riecki, 2018). If these needs are met, individuals are more likely to experience positive emotions (Berry et al., 2020). Similarly, the SDT suggests that students who feel competent and in control of their studies are more likely to experience positive emotions, such as higher happiness levels (Chui, 2021). This is because feeling competent satisfies one of the basic psychological needs identified by the SDT (Lim et al., 2021).

When Golden Faith Academy Senior High School students are happy, the Broaden-and-Build Theory will take place, suggesting better academic performance. Better academic performance can also mean competitiveness, and this is where the SDT comes in, resulting to a higher level of happiness. Then, the process goes back and forth, forming a correlation between the two variables. However, these variables have other variables that can influence their relationship, like grade level, gender, strand, and family type. These variables are called the moderating variables and it is important for researchers to control their influence (see *Figure 1*).

IV. Methodology

This chapter presents the methods used in this paper. The purpose is to justify the selection of these methods and provide detailed descriptions of how they were implemented. This ensures the validity and reliability of the study's results.

A. Research Design

The Quantitative Research Design (QRD) of this study is associational, under the subtype of correlational research. Correlational research analyzes the relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them (Seeram, 2019). Similarly, this study focuses on identifying the relationship between the level of happiness and academic performance. The choice of this research design is consistent with studies that explored the association between these variables (Abadi et al., 2015; Gunasekara & Jayasekara, 2019). This is an effective approach because it can also identify the strength and direction of this relationship (Basnet et al., 2023).

B. Variables

This study does not have an independent or dependent variable as it uses a correlational research design. However, the main variables of this study are level of happiness and academic performance. The level of happiness and academic performance will be measured using an interval and ratio measurement, respectively. The General Weighted Average (GWA) will be used to assess the academic performance of students, while the Oxford Happiness Questionnaire (OHQ) short form will be used to measure their level of happiness. The researchers also identified several moderating variables, namely grade level, gender, strand, and family type. These moderating variables can influence or change the relationship between the two main variables (Ablen et al., 2021; Boye-Laryea, 2020; Langevin, 2013; Liu et al., 2023; Mertoglu, 2020; Santos, 2019). Moderating variables will also be measured using the nominal measurement. To minimize the impact of these moderating variables, the researchers will include them in the basic questions of the research instrument.

C. Research Instrument

The research instrument used has instructions, questionnaire, and interpretation. Instructions provide guidance on completing the questionnaire. The questionnaire itself is divided into basic and complex questions. The basic questions collect the grade level, gender, strand, and family type, as well as the

respondents' GWA. This approach can help identify the influence of the four moderating variables and measure the respondents' academic performance.

The complex questions, on the other hand, focus on measuring the respondents' level of happiness. A valid and reliable research instrument like the OHQ is required for this variable. The OHQ is a 29-item questionnaire on a 6-point Likert scale developed by Michael Argyle and Peter Hills (Arefi et al., 2023). It also has a short form, which consists of eight questions that this study will utilize.

The OHQ short form questionnaire is recognized as a reliable and valid tool for measuring the respondents' level of happiness. The validity of this questionnaire was confirmed through factor analysis (Almadani & Alwesmi, 2023). The reliability of the items is acceptable with a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.71 (Balootbangan et al., 2016). Meanwhile, the last part of the questionnaire is interpretation. It consists of how to compute the happiness score. The happiness scores can be interpreted using Stephen Wright's interpretation. These include "not happy" (1-2), "somewhat unhappy" (2-3), "not particularly happy or unhappy" (3-4), "somewhat happy or moderately happy" (4), "rather happy; pretty happy" (4-5), "very happy" (5-6), and "too happy" (6).

D. Unit of Analysis and Sampling

The unit of analysis for this study is the Golden Faith Academy Senior High School students. The researchers have chosen to examine a sample of the population to ensure the study's feasibility. They will use a probability sampling method called simple random sampling. Simple random sampling is a probability sampling method where researchers randomly choose respondents from a given sample (West, 2016). This is deemed effective to eliminate potential biases from the researchers (Golzar et al., 2022).

E. Data Gathering

The researchers used the Google Forms to collect data and designed it based on the research instrument of this study. Proper notes explaining that participation is voluntary and that their privacy and confidentiality will be respected are included. Following that, the researchers sought approval from the admin of the Golden Faith Academy Senior High School faculty by submitting a letter request that outlined the purpose and ethical considerations of the study. After the approval was granted, the researchers sent the Google Forms to the respondents' email addresses. The data gathering lasted for seven days to allow them to respond at their most convenient time. There were 2252 total responses that were collected at the end of the data gathering period.

F. Data Analysis

The researchers will use the mean to assess the central tendency of both the level of happiness and academic performance. The mean is a commonly used measure of central tendency for normally distributed data (Cardinal, 2015). This approach is deemed suitable given the application of the Central Limit Theorem (CLT), which states that a large sample will be approximately normally distributed (Kim & Kwak, 2017). Since there is a large sample that is gathered in this study, the CLT is applicable. Standard deviation will also be used to identify the data's dispersion because it is often paired with the mean (El Omda & Sergent, 2022). In addition, moderating variables will be described using the mode as they have categorical data (Yellapu, 2018). Measures of dispersion are not applicable for these variables but researchers may use percentages instead (Gogtay & Hazra, 2016).

For statistical treatment, it is important to first examine whether the main and moderating variables should undergo parametric or non-parametric analysis. For the variables to be eligible for parametric analysis, they must meet four criteria: normal distribution, homoscedasticity, interval or ratio measurement, and probability sampling. If any of these conditions are not met, non-parametric statistics will be used.

The normality of the data for each variable is tested using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. It is a type of statistical test that is used to determine the normality of a numerical dataset (Gupta et al., 2019; Muhammad, 2020). As such, the moderating variables are not applicable for this test and only variables with numerical data like level of happiness and academic performance are allowed. The results from this test revealed that the academic performance ($4.126e-12 < 0.05$) and level of happiness ($3.403e-12 < 0.05$) are not normally distributed.

Meanwhile, homoscedasticity states that the spread or dispersion of data points is equal throughout the range of the independent variable (Kibra & Sharma, 2013). It can be tested using Levene's test, which examines whether the variances of the dependent variable are equal across different groups (Conover et al., 2018). Since this is a correlational study, the focus is on examining the relationship, not comparing groups. As such, the researchers can disregard the second condition and assess the remaining ones.

Moreover, the moderating variables did not satisfy the third condition as they used the nominal measurement. The main variables, on the other hand, satisfy this condition because the level of happiness and academic performance employed interval and ratio measurements, respectively. Additionally, all variables in this study satisfy the fourth condition, as it uses probability sampling, specifically simple random sampling.

Therefore, there are no variables in this study that meet all the conditions for parametric statistics. Non-parametric statistics will be used instead. Among other non-parametric statistical treatments, Spearman's

rho is the most suitable for identifying relationships. Spearman's rho, or Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, is a statistical treatment that can determine the strength and direction of the relationship using the ranks of the two variables. Similar studies have also used this statistical treatment to identify the relationship between level of happiness and academic performance (Lumontod, 2018; Zulkifli, 2013; Abadi et al., 2015; Zulkifli, 2013).

V. Results, Analysis and Discussions

This chapter presents the overall results of the study. It also provides analysis and discussion of the variables being studied. This chapter also aims to answer the research questions with the use of statistics.

A. Results

The respondents consist of 2252 Golden Faith Academy Senior High School students. There are 1034 Grade 11 students (45.9%) and 1218 Grade 12 students (54.1%) in the tally (see *Figure 1*).

Figure 2. Respondents' Distribution per Grade Level

Majority of the respondents are female, which consists of 1,392 (61.8%) students. There are also 860 (38.2%) of male students (see *Figure 2*). The mode is Grade 12 as they are the most frequent.

Figure 3. Respondents' Distribution per Gender

Out of the total respondents, there are 860 (38.2%) STEM, 665 (29.5%) ABM, 426 (18.9%) HUMSS, 261 (11.6%) ICT, and 40 (1.8%) TOUR students (see Figure 3).

Figure 4. Respondents' Distribution per Strand

The data also revealed that there are 531 (23.6%) students from a broken family and 1,721 (76.4%) from a non-broken family (see Figure 4).

Figure 5. Respondents' Distribution per Family Type

The academic performance is tested using the GWA. The average grade of Golden Faith Academy Senior High School students is 90.4, with a standard deviation of 5.4. Meanwhile, the level of happiness is measured using the OHQ short form. The calculated mean is 3.3, which can be classified as "somewhat happy or moderately happy." The standard deviation is 1.31.

B. Analysis

The researchers determine whether the main variables, academic performance and level of happiness, should be analyzed using parametric or non-parametric statistics. Moderating variables, including grade level, gender, strand, and family status, will also be included. For the variables to be eligible for parametric statistics, they must meet four conditions: normal distribution, homoscedasticity, interval or ratio measurement, and probability sampling. If any of these conditions are not met, non-parametric statistics will be used.

The normality of the data is tested using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. It is a type of statistical test that is used to determine the normality of a numerical dataset (Gupta et al., 2019; Muhammad, 2020). This means that the moderating variables are not applicable for this test. Only variables with a numerical dataset, like level of happiness and academic performance, are allowed. The calculated p-value of academic performance from this test is $4.126e-12$, which is less than the significance level of 0.05. This indicates that the data is not normally distributed. The level of happiness also has a not normally distributed data, with a calculated p-value of $3.403e-12$.

Meanwhile, homoscedasticity states that the spread or dispersion of data points is equal throughout the range of the independent variable. It can be tested using Levene's test. This test examines whether the variances of the dependent variable are equal across different groups or levels of the independent variable (Conover et al., 2018; Kibra & Sharma, 2013). Since this is a correlational study, the focus is on examining the relationship between two variables, not comparing groups. As such, the researchers can disregard the second condition and assess the remaining ones.

Moreover, the moderating variables did not satisfy the third condition as they used the nominal measurement. The main variables, on the other hand, satisfy this condition because the level of happiness and academic performance employed interval and ratio measurements, respectively. Additionally, all variables in this study satisfy the fourth condition, as it uses probability sampling, specifically simple random sampling.

Therefore, there are no variables in this study that meet all the conditions for parametric statistics. Non-parametric statistics will be used instead. Among other non-parametric statistical treatments, Spearman's rho is the most suitable for identifying relationships. Spearman's rho, or Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, is a statistical treatment that can determine the strength and direction of the relationship using the ranks of the two variables. Similar studies have also used this statistical treatment to identify the relationship between level of happiness and academic performance (Abadi et al., 2015; Zulkifli, 2013).

Furthermore, the moderating variables will also be tested using Spearman's rho to identify their relationship with the two main variables. These variables undergo a step-by-step process. First, the researchers identified variables that could be categorized. Second, they brainstormed the relevance of each

identified variable to the study. Any irrelevant moderating variables were removed and will be used as recommendations for future studies. These steps were repeated until all the necessary moderating variables were identified.

Results from Spearman's rho revealed a very weak positive relationship between academic performance and level of happiness ($r_s=0.1101$). Similarly, the moderating variables, namely grade level, gender, strand, and family status, all have a very weak positive relationship with the two main variables (see Figure 6, Figure 7 Figure 8, & Figure 9).

	Spearman's Rho	Relationship
Grade 11	0.07284	Very Weak Positive Relationship
Grade 12	0.1003	Very Weak Positive Relationship

Figure 6. Results of Spearman's Rho for the Relationship of Grade Level on Level of Happiness and Academic Performance

	Spearman's Rho	Relationship
Male	0.1462	Very Weak Positive Relationship
Female	0.0971	Very Weak Positive Relationship

Figure 7. Results of Spearman's Rho for the Relationship of Gender on Level of Happiness and Academic Performance

	Spearman's Rho	Relationship
STEM	0.07419	Very Weak Positive Relationship
ABM	0.1451	Very Weak Positive Relationship
HUMSS	0.1011	Very Weak Positive Relationship
ICT	0.1628	Very Weak Positive Relationship
TOUR	0.04564	Very Weak Positive Relationship

Figure 8. Results of Spearman's Rho for the Relationship of Strand on Level of Happiness and Academic Performance

	Spearman's Rho	Relationship
Broken	0.06391	Very Weak Positive Relationship
Non-Broken	0.1258	Very Weak Positive Relationship

Figure 9. Results of Spearman's Rho for the Relationship of Family Type on Level of Happiness and Academic Performance

C. Discussions

There is a significant but very weak positive relationship between level of happiness and academic performance. This means that the positive impact of a level of happiness on academic performance is that when students are happier, they may have higher academic performance. The negative impact of a low level of happiness is that students may also have lower academic performance. It is also important to note that since the strength is very weak, the effect size is relatively small. Similarly, the moderating variables, namely grade level, gender, strand, and family status, all have a very weak positive relationship with the two main variables.

To achieve these results, data cleaning was first done, followed by identifying if the data required parametric statistics. The Spearman's Rho helped researchers identify the relationship between the variables from a not normally distributed data. However, these results are different from previous studies, as most have found no correlation between the level of happiness and academic performance (Annisa, 2022; Gunasekara & Jayasekara, 2019). Nevertheless, these findings are still important, as most studies similar to this have been conducted in foreign countries, thereby fulfilling the research gap that this study seeks to address.

VI. Conclusion and Recommendations

This chapter presents the conclusion and recommendations of this study. The conclusion part summarizes the important findings of this study. The recommendation part provides suggestions for future research.

A. Conclusion

Therefore, there is a significant very weak positive relationship between the level of happiness and academic performance. This means that when students are happier they can have higher academic performance. If students have a low happiness level they can have lower academic performance. However, the

strength is very weak. This also implies that happiness should not be the sole focus when it comes to academic success. Similarly, grade level, gender, strand, and family type has also a significant very weak positive relationship between the level of happiness and academic performance.

B. Recommendations

Future research may explore the level of happiness and academic performance from a different sample. They can also include different moderating variables like socioeconomic status and age. Additionally, they can also compare the level of happiness across different groups.

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APPENDIX

Oxford Happiness Questionnaire Short Form

Instructions: To complete the questionnaire, first answer the basic questions with honesty. Then, carefully read each statement. Select the number that best represents your level of agreement or disagreement, ranging from (1) strongly disagree to (6) strongly agree. Remember that there are no right or wrong answers. The first answer that comes to your head is probably the right one for you.

Basic Questions:

- Grade Level:
- Gender:
- Strand:
- Family Type:

Statements:

1. I don't feel particularly pleased with the way I am. (R)
2. I am intensely interested in other people.
3. I feel that life is very rewarding.
4. I have very warm feelings towards almost everyone.
5. I rarely wake up feeling rested. (R)
6. I am not particularly optimistic about the future. (R)
7. I find most things amusing.
8. I am always committed and involved.

Interpretation:

1. Items marked (R) should be scored in reverse:
For example, if you gave yourself a "1," cross it out and change it to a "6."
Change "2" to a "5"
Change "3" to a "4"
Change "4" to a "3"
Change "5" to a "2"
Change "6" to a "1"
2. Add the numbers for all 8 statements. (Use the converted numbers for the 3 statements that are reverse scored.)
3. Divide the computed number in Step 2 by 8.
4. Classify your happiness score in Step 3 using Stephen Wright's interpretation:
1-2: Not happy
2-3: Somewhat unhappy
3-4: Not particular happy
4: Somewhat happy or moderately happy
4-5: Rather happy or pretty happy
5-6: Very happy
6: Too Happy